

Types of Bone Grafts

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"The only rationale form of treatment is that which calls forth the recuperative powers of the body."

— **John Hunter (1793)**

Since the inception of dental science, the specialities of periodontics and restorative dentistry have worked diligently to save dentition and provide the optimum level of health to the oral cavity. Periodontics focuses on preventive and corrective procedures for saving natural teeth affected by periodontitis.

Periodontitis causes loss of tooth-supporting bone, and the bone loss may be vertical, horizontal, or combined. The desired ideal outcome is the regeneration, possible to some extent with the use of various kinds of bone grafting materials, available in different forms.^[1] Increasing probing depths with the increasing severity of periodontal disease have been consistently associated with the infra bony defects. Clinical studies have proven that residual pockets often persist after nonsurgical periodontal therapy or the use of access flaps, and respective techniques are associated with substantial loss of attachment and increases in soft tissue recession. Along with this, such techniques are characterized by repair (i.e., formation of long junctional epithelium) rather than regeneration (i.e., formation of root cementum with functionally oriented inserting periodontal ligament fibers connected to a new alveolar bone).

To achieve predictable periodontal regeneration, various surgical techniques, including implantation of various types of bone grafts and substitutes, root surface demineralization, guided tissue regeneration, growth and differentiation factors, and enamel matrix proteins, or various combinations thereof, have been employed. Overall, results demonstrate that flap surgery in conjunction with most evaluated biomaterials promotes periodontal regeneration to a greater extent than flap surgery without biomaterials.^[1]

Several types of bone grafts have been studied over the years, and periodontists continue to search for ideal materials. The two most common types of graft material used in periodontics today are autogenous and allogenic.

Ideal requirements of graft:

The main function of bone grafts is to provide mechanical support and stimulate osteo-regeneration, with the ultimate goal of bone replacement.^[2] The four fundamental biological properties of osseointegration, osteogenesis, osteo-conduction, and osteoinduction are paramount in performing this role effectively.^[3,4] Osseointegration refers to the ability of grafting material to chemically bond to the bone's surface in the absence of an intervening fibrous tissue layer. Osteoinduction is the recruitment of host stem cells into the grafting site, where local proteins and other factors induce the differentiation of

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stem cells into osteoblasts.^[1] Osteogenesis is the formation of new bone, occurring when viable osteoblasts and/or osteoblast precursors are transplanted with the bone. Osteoblast precursors differentiate into mature osteoblasts under appropriate host conditions. Since few mature osteoblasts survive transplantation of a nonvascularized bone graft, the stem cells are responsible for a significant portion of new bone formation. Osteoblast precursors are found in bone, bone marrow, periosteum, and other tissues. Osteoconduction refers to a bone graft or implant's ability to provide a structural framework on which host cells reconstitute. This scaffold enables the ingrowth of vessels, osteoblasts, and stem cells so that union occurs with the host skeleton. If ingrowth does not occur, then nonunion and inadequate strength may result. Both viable and nonviable materials may possess osteoconductive properties. Important structural properties include porosity, pore size, pore connectivity, and surface roughness. Osteoconduction is limited, however, by factors such as the size of the defect, cellularity of the recipient bed, contact with donor tissue, passive ingrowth of new bone from the

recipient bed, and host regulation of resorption and remodeling. Osteoinduction is the recruitment of stem cells from the host bed into the graft site, where they differentiate into osteoblasts. Several growth factors that influence this process are bone morphogenic proteins (BMPs), platelet-derived growth factors, insulin-like growth factors (I and II), fibroblast growth factors (acidic and basic), epidermal growth factor, TGF-B (B1 and B2), and retinoic acid.^[1]

The success percentage of a bone graft will also be influenced by an array of other characteristics. These comprise but are not restricted to, the following: affordability, simplicity of handling, plasticity, vascular ingrowth-adequate porosity, sterility, structural integrity, biocompatibility, bioresorbability, and compressive strength.

Creeping substitution refers to the movement of new tissue through channels made by blood vessels invading a transplanted bone. Bone transplants undergo necrosis, and that necrotic bone is replaced by new bone via creeping substitution.^[5]

Types of bone grafts:

Type of Bone Graft	Source	Description
Autografts		
Bone Autografts	Patient's own body	Bone harvested from patient (e.g., iliac crest, mandibular symphysis) and transplanted to target site.
Allografts		
Human Allografts	Cadaveric bone	Donor bone sourced from a human cadaver, processed to remove potential infectious agents.
Xenografts		
Bovine Xenografts	Bovine (cow) bone	Processed bovine bone devoid of organic components, providing a mineralized scaffold for bone regeneration.
Alloplasts		
Synthetic Bone Grafts	Artificial materials (e.g., hydroxy-apatite, tricalcium phosphate)	Synthetic materials mimicking natural bone properties.
Demineralized Freeze-Dried Bone Allografts (DFDBA)	Cadaveric bone	Cadaveric bone with mineral content removed, leaving a collagen matrix and growth factors for bone growth.

Autogenous Grafts^[6]

Autogenous grafts are considered the gold standard as they retain the viability of cells and do not evoke any immunological response in the patient. These grafts contain live osteoblasts and osteoprogenitor stem cells and heal by osteogenesis. They constitute all three components for tissue engineering, namely, scaffold, cells, and signaling molecules as an additional benefit.

In the presence of adequate vascularization, osteoprogenitor cells (or preosteoblasts) proliferate and bridge the gap between the graft and the recipient bone. The preosteoblasts also generally form the first deposits of new bone. Transplanted osteocytes usually die in response to anoxia and surgical injury but can survive transplantation and may initiate the resorption of the graft.

The micro anastomoses form and restore circulation and are vital for the survival of osteoprogenitor cells and the formation of new products by the cells. New bone is formed initially by the surviving cells in the graft and later by the osteoinduction of the cells of the surrounding host bone. The area of new bone interdigitation and the quantity of donor bone that is resorbed are higher for cancellous bone grafts compared with cortical grafts.^[2]

Periodontal defects at the sites of bone grafting are unique as they are contaminated by saliva. Ellegard Scallhorn^[7] defined the governing criteria for the selection of grafts for periodontal use. They are biological acceptability, predictability, clinical feasibility, minimal operative hazards, minimal postoperative sequelae and patients' acceptance regarding the source and the cost of the material.

Mechanism

Osteoprogenitor cells, also known as preosteoblasts, multiply and deposit the first bone upon sufficient vascularization; transplanted osteocytes perish from anoxia and surgical trauma; transplanted osteoclasts that made it through transplantation start the graft's resorption; and micro anastomoses restore circulation. The cells that have survived begin to form new bone, which is subsequently formed by osteoinduction.

Sources of Autogenous Grafts

Autogenous bone can be harvested from intraoral donor sites (mandibular symphysis and ramus, maxillary tuberosity, edentulous areas, tori) or extraoral sites (iliac crest, tibia, calvaria).^[8]

Although the iliac crest is one of the most preferred sites, it is not always recommended due to its associated problems such as postoperative infection, exfoliation, sequestration, varying rates of healing, root resorption, and rapid recurrence of defects. In addition to patient expense; patient morbidity, altered ambulation, difficulty in procuring the donor material, and need for hospitalization were the limiting factors.^[9,10] These disadvantages, along with the fact that the alveolar defects do not demand large amounts of bone, led to the growing use of intraoral grafts. Intraoral donor sites have the benefit of conventional surgical access, proximity of donor and recipient sites, reducing operative time and anesthesia time, discomfort to patients, and less morbidity compared to extraoral locations, making it ideal for outpatient periodontal surgery.

Although several donor sites have been described, there is no clear preference indicated in the literature for any specific donor site.^[10,11]

Types of Autogenous Bone Graft

Several types of autogenous bone grafts have been or are being used clinically. They include bone chips, osseous coagulum, bone blend intraoral, and extraoral cancellous bone and marrow.

Autogenous Bone Block

Autogenous Cortical Bone Chips

Cortical Bone Graft

Autogenous cortical bone graft, which provides an osteoconductive medium with minimal osteoinductive and osteogenic properties, is best suited for structural defects for which immediate mechanical stability is required for healing. The dense cortical matrix results in relatively slow revascularization and incorporation, as resorption must occur before the deposition of new bone, and limited perfusion and donor osteocytes make this option poorly osteogenic.^[12,13]

For periodontal defects, Nabers and O' Leary (1965) have reported a coronal increase in bone height by using cortical bone chips, removed by hand chisels during osteoplasty and ostectomy. Cortical bone chips due to their relatively large particle size $1,559.6 \times 183 \mu\text{m}$ and potential for sequestration were replaced by autogenous osseous coagulum and bone blend.^[7] The literature indicated a broad range when considering the influence of particle size for autologous bone grafts. Values from $125 \mu\text{m}$ upto 2 mm were reported as preferable. A critical minimum value was reported stating that particles less than $75\text{-}125 \mu\text{m}$ are rapidly resorbed, and do not participate in effective osteogenesis.

Cancellous Bone Graft

Cancellous bone graft is the most commonly used source of autogenous graft. It provides an osteoinductive, osteoconductive, and osteogenic substrate, and the porous trabeculae are lined with functional osteoblasts, resulting in a highly osteogenic graft.

After implantation, a portion of the donor osteocytes survives, and these osteocytes, combined with graft porosity and local cytokines, promote angiogenesis and host mesenchymal stem cell recruitment.^[14]

Corticocancellous Bone Graft

Corticocancellous bone grafts intuitively offer the advantages of both cortical bone and cancellous bone, an osteoconductive medium and, immediate structural stability from cortical bone, and the osteoinductive and osteogenic capabilities of cancellous bone.

Intraoral Cancellous Bone And Marrow

Intraoral cancellous bone and marrow can be obtained from healing extraction sockets, mandibular retromolar areas, and maxillary tuberosity areas. A mean bone fill of 3.65 mm and $>50\%$ bone fill has been obtained on a predictable basis.^[13]

Extraoral Cancellous Bone And Marrow

This material is obtained from either the anterior or the posterior iliac crest predictable bone growth ranging $3.53\text{-}4.36 \text{ mm}$ and even complete eradication of furcation involvement and interdental craters have been reported by various authors.^[11,12,13]

Osseous Coagulum And Bone Blend

Intraoral bone, when obtained with high or low-speed round burs and mixed with blood becomes a coagulum.^[15] It was subsequently demonstrated in monkeys that small bone particles of $100 \mu\text{m}$ could provide an earlier and greater osteogenic activity than particles 10 times as large.^[7]

The bone blend technique was designed to overcome some of the disadvantages of osseous coagulum including inability to aspirate during the collection process and unknown quality and fluidity of the material. Bone blend is cortical or cancellous bone that is procured with a trephine or rongeurs, placed in an amalgam capsule and triturated to the consistency of a slushy osseous mass. The resultant particle size is in the range of $210 \times 105 \mu\text{m}$.^[16] Froum et al. reported that the osseous coagulum bone blend type of grafts provided 2.98 mm coronal growth of the alveolar bone, compared with 0.66 mm obtained when open flap debridement alone was used.^[17]

Bone Allografts

It is not possible sometimes to procure enough amounts of autogenous grafts and it involves the second surgical site for the patient. Along with this the quality and quantity of bone are not consistent. This led to the search for materials that have the properties of autogenous grafts without the limitations of amount and avoiding the second surgical site for the patients. This led to the development of allografts which are the grafts.

Allograft place

Freeze dried, irradiated demineralized bone granules

Allografts in Periodontics ^[18,19,20,21,22]

Introduction

Allografts play a pivotal role in contemporary periodontics, providing clinicians with a versatile and effective option for addressing bone defects resulting from periodontal disease, trauma, or surgical procedures.

Allograft materials might come from cadaveric bone sources or a suitable living donor. There are three main ways to prepare allograft materials: fresh, frozen, or freeze-dried. Fresh and frozen allograft materials have better osteoinductive qualities but are rarely employed due to increased danger of disease transmission, shorter shelf life, and a higher likelihood of a host immunogenic response.

Characteristics of Allografts

Allografts are derived from human donors and can be sourced from various bones, such as special structural bones (iliac crest), long bones (femur), or a combination. The processing techniques eliminate cellular components while preserving the mineralized bone matrix. The resultant material serves as a scaffold for the host's cells to infiltrate and regenerate.

Advantages of Allografts

Good histocompatibility is exhibited by allografts, which come in a variety of forms, including entire bone segments, cortico-cancellous and cortical fragments, chips, wedges, pegs, powder, and DBM. Additionally, materials for allografts can be made into specific shapes to meet recipient sites' specifications.

Disadvantages of Allografts

Unfortunately, cancellous autografts and allografts lack mechanical strength, and cancellous allografts also show insufficient ability to heal because the materials' osteoinductive properties are diminished by tissue processing methods that involve the use of alcohol, acetic acid, or nitric acid. Cancellous allografts may induce an inflammatory response in the local host, leading to the production of fibrous tissue that may obstruct the formation of new bone. Similar to cortical autografts, cortical allografts have a high degree of mechanical strength and are primarily used to create a mechanical scaffold on which the processes leading up to bone healing can take place after an initial inflammatory cascade. Allografts have been utilized in dentistry to treat mandibular, maxillary, and periodontal abnormalities. To provide enough bone height for implant insertion, block allografts have frequently been utilized to correct inadequacies in alveolar ridge height or severe ridge atrophy. Cancellous allografts may induce an inflammatory response in the local host, leading to the production of fibrous tissue that may obstruct the formation of new bone. An allograft derivative known as demineralized bone matrix is acid-treated to eliminate the mineral mesh. The underlying inner bone matrix, which is rich in growth hormones including TGF- β and FGF as well as bone morphogenic protein (BMP), is revealed by this demineralization process. These growth factors can induce mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) to differentiate into osteoblasts, giving them a higher capability for osteoinduction than cortical or cancellous allografts. Even with the remaining osteoinductive molecules, tissue preparation methods like these have a significant impact on DBM's osteoinductive capability.^[23]

Clinical Applications

- 1. Ridge Augmentation:** Allografts are commonly employed in ridge augmentation procedures to restore lost bone volume in preparation for dental implant placement.
- 2. Socket Preservation:** Following tooth extraction, allografts help maintain socket dimensions, minimizing bone resorption and preserving the surrounding anatomy.
- 3. Periodontal Defects:** Allografts are utilized in the treatment of intrabony defects and furcation involvement, promoting periodontal regeneration.
- 4. Sinus Floor Augmentation:** In sinus lift procedures, allografts serve as a reliable option for enhancing bone height in the maxillary sinus.

Limitations and Considerations

1. **Resorption Rate:** Allograft resorption rates may vary, necessitating careful consideration of the specific graft material and patient factors.
2. **Immunogenic Potential:** While processing minimizes immunogenicity, allografts still pose a risk of immune response, especially in certain patient populations.
3. **Cost:** Allografts may be more expensive than other graft materials, impacting treatment costs.

Conclusion

Allografts have emerged as valuable tools in periodontics, offering a biocompatible and osteoconductive solution for a range of clinical applications. The careful consideration of patient-specific factors, graft characteristics, and the latest advancements in processing techniques ensures optimal outcomes. Continued research and clinical studies will further enhance our understanding of allografts and their evolving role in periodontal therapy.

Xenografts in Periodontics:

Introduction

Xenografts, derived from animal sources, have become integral in addressing bone defects in periodontics. Deproteinized bovine bone, sold commercially under the brand name BioOss™, is the most popular source of xenograft materials in the dental industry. Stepwise annealing of the bone is followed by a chemical treatment with NaOH to create a porous hydroxyapatite (HA) substance that only contains the inorganic parts of the bone. The resulting porous structure can promote bone healing through osteoconduction and offer strong mechanical support because it closely resembles real bone. The porous structure has a large surface area and encourages angiogenesis, which stimulates the formation of new blood vessels and improves bone growth.

Osseograft placed in defect

Osseograft

Characteristics of Xenografts

Xenografts are typically sourced from animals such as cows (bovine) or pigs (porcine). These grafts undergo meticulous processing to eliminate antigens and minimize the risk of immunogenic reactions. Xenografts retain a natural bone mineral structure and offer osteoconductive properties conducive to new bone formation.

Clinical Applications

There are other commercially available products made from bovine bone, like OsteoGraft™ and Cerabone™. Since all organic components are removed through high-temperature treatment, both compounds have low immunogenicity. These goods, like BioOss™, have structural and biochemical characteristics that are strikingly similar to those of human bone and can be used as osteoconductive grafting materials.

Chitosan, a naturally occurring polymer made of glucosamine and N-acetylglucosamine extracted from the exoskeletons of crustaceans, is a promising xenograft material. By offering a structural framework that promotes osteoblastic activity, forming a mineralized bone matrix, and encouraging MSC differentiation into osteoblasts in a variety of in vitro settings, chitosan can promote bone regeneration.^[48] There are several different ways to get chitosan; they include films, beads, hydrogels, and more intricate structures such as porous scaffolds. Because

chitosan has poor mechanical qualities, it is frequently mixed with other materials to create more desirable features, like gelatin, calcium phosphates, and bioglass.

- 1. Ridge Augmentation:** Xenografts are commonly employed for ridge augmentation, enhancing bone volume and morphology to facilitate successful dental implant placement.
- 2. Socket Preservation:** After tooth extraction, xenografts help preserve socket dimensions, preventing excessive bone resorption and maintaining the integrity of the surrounding alveolar bone.
- 3. Periodontal Defects:** Xenografts play a vital role in the treatment of intrabony defects and furcation involvement, supporting periodontal regeneration and attachment.
- 4. Sinus Floor Augmentation:** In sinus lift procedures, xenografts serve as a reliable option for augmenting the sinus floor, creating a stable foundation for dental implant placement in the posterior maxilla.

Advantages of Xenografts

- 1. Osteoconductivity:** Xenografts provide an osteoconductive matrix, promoting the ingrowth of host bone and facilitating successful osseointegration.
- 2. Availability:** Xenograft materials are widely available, making them a convenient option for clinicians.
- 3. Biocompatibility:** Processed xenografts exhibit excellent biocompatibility, reducing the risk of adverse reactions in the host.

Limitations and Considerations

- 1. Resorption Rate:** Xenograft resorption rates may vary, necessitating careful consideration of the specific graft material and the clinical scenario.
- 2. Immunogenic Potential:** Despite processing, xenografts may still carry a risk of immune response in some patients.
- 3. Cost:** While generally more cost-effective than autografts, xenografts may be more expensive than some synthetic alternatives.

Recent Advancements

Recent research has focused on enhancing the biological properties of xenografts, such as incorporating growth factors or combining them with other biomaterials to improve clinical outcomes.

Conclusion

Xenografts have proven to be versatile and reliable in addressing various periodontal challenges. Their osteoconductive properties, biocompatibility, and broad availability make them valuable tools in contemporary periodontics. However, careful patient selection, consideration of graft resorption rates, and ongoing research are crucial for optimizing the efficacy of xenografts in periodontal therapy.

Alloplasts in Periodontics:

Introduction

Artificial synthetic bone replacement materials that closely resemble the biological characteristics of genuine bone are created to help overcome potential immunogenicity and morbidity at donor sites. Despite this, currently available synthetic materials demonstrate only osteointegrative and osteoconductive properties^[14]. This group of materials includes metals like nickel-titanium, polymers like polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), polyglycolides, calcium phosphate cements, and calcium phosphate ceramics like hydroxyapatite (HA), tricalcium phosphate (TCP), and bioglass Alloplasts, have gained prominence in periodontics as alternatives to biological grafts.

Characteristics of Alloplasts

Alloplasts are composed of synthetic materials, typically ceramics such as hydroxyapatite (HA) and tricalcium phosphate (TCP). These materials are biocompatible and designed to mimic the mineral composition of natural bone. Alloplasts may be used alone or in combination with other biomaterials to enhance their properties.

Hydroxyapatite (HA)^[25,26]

Because of its chemical makeup, which is similar to that of the inorganic component of bone, HA can be employed as a material for bone grafting. But unlike naturally generated HA, like that found in cow bone, synthetic HA lacks trace levels of Na⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, and Sr⁺, which can affect a variety of biomechanical processes. Unlike HA obtained from cows, synthetic HA lacks a microporous structure. Because of its high crystallinity and relatively high Ca/P ratio, synthetic HA has a delayed resorption rate. The comparatively poor mechanical strength of HA, which

prohibits its application at high load-bearing places, is another significant issue with the material. In the realm of HA-based bone substitute materials, recent developments have focused on generating nanosized HA, which exhibits improved biomechanical capabilities and more closely resembles the makeup of natural bone. The rationale behind the creation of these materials at the nanoscale is their striking resemblance to the extracellular matrix of bone, their ability to respond to external stimuli more quickly, and their improved delivery and controlled release of bioactive molecules, like growth factors which enable enhanced osteoregenerative properties.^[27]

Tricalcium Phosphate^[28,29]

There are two crystallographic forms of Tricalcium Phosphate Ceramics (β -TCP): α -TCP and β -TCP. For many years, β -TCP, a kind of calcium phosphate substance, was utilised as a bone substitute. Because of its lower Ca/P ratio, it shows faster biodegradation and absorption than HA. Pure phasic β -TCP has many advantageous qualities, including low immunogenicity and disease transmission risk, good resorbability in comparison to bovine bone grafts, good osteoconductivity because of macroporosity that promotes fibrovascular ingrowth and osteogenic cell adhesion, radiopacity that permits monitoring of healing, and easy handling. Although β -TCP's linked porous structure promotes better vascularization, it also makes the material less mechanically strong when compressed. Biphasic Calcium Phosphate Ceramics (HA and β -TCP Ceramics)^[27,28,29,30,31]

Over the past few decades, researchers have worked to create a material that can combine the osteoconductive properties of HA with the resorbability of β -TCP. As a result, biphasic calcium phosphate ceramics were created, in which β -TCP and HA are frequently combined. Therefore, the primary advantages of adopting biphasic CP ceramics are their stronger mechanical qualities compared to β -TCP alone and their faster and higher rates of bone regeneration when compared to the use of HA alone. Furthermore, biphasic calcium phosphate ceramics' osteoconductivity and resorption can be managed by adjusting the HA/ β -TCP ratio.

Bioactive Glass^[32,33,34]

The term "bioactive glasses" (BAG) refers to a kind of ceramics made of synthetic silicates combined with additional minerals, such as calcium, sodium hydroxide, phosphorus, and sulphur. Bioglass's initial composition was

silicon dioxide (SiO_2), sodium oxide (Na_2O), calcium oxide (CaO), and phosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5). However, potassium oxide (K_2O), magnesium oxide (MgO), and boric oxide (B_2O) have since been added to the mixture to make it more stable. When the material is exposed to bodily fluids during implantation, silicon ions have the potential to seep out and build up, creating a coating of HA on the surface that promotes osteogenic progenitor cell adhesion. Good biocompatibility, osteoconductivity, antibacterial activity, and a porous structure that encourages vascularization are among the desired characteristics of bioglass.^[35,36]

Calcium Sulphate Cement^[37]

Calcium phosphate cement systems are often composed of two or three components: an aqueous component and a powder component that typically contains sintered calcium phosphate material, like α -TCP and HA. After the ingredients are combined, a workable paste is produced that, at room temperature, self-sets to create HA nanocrystals in situ^[17,141]. The primary benefits of CPCs are their osteoconductive qualities, high biocompatibility, self-setting capability, ability to mould the paste into the defect site, ability to replicate the structure and composition of bone in a repeatable manner, and availability in various forms for various types of bony defects^[3,11,141]. Nevertheless, the absence of a macroporous structure in CPC restricts the rate of fluid exchange, restorability, and cell adhesion.

Polymers^[38,39]

Subtypes of synthetic polymers that are degradable and non-degradable can be further categorised. Polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid, poly ϵ -caprolactone, and their copolymers and derivatives are the most often utilised polymers for bone regeneration; taken together, these are referred to as aliphatic polyesters^[12,17]. This class of materials' primary benefits are their physiochemical structure, low immunogenicity, adjustable resorbability, porosity, and configurable shapes^[12,154]. However, there are issues with low cell attachment capability, osteoconductivity, and the release of acidic breakdown products that change the local pH. HTR Synthetic Bone™ is an example of a commercially available polymer-based bone substitute material composed of PMMA, polyhydroxyethylmethacrylate, and calcium hydroxide. This product has been successfully used in the management of periodontal intrabony and furcation defects.

Clinical Applications

- 1. Ridge Augmentation:** Alloplasts are commonly employed for ridge augmentation procedures, aiding in the reconstruction of bone volume to support subsequent implant placement.
- 2. Socket Preservation:** Following tooth extraction, alloplasts help maintain socket dimensions, preventing the collapse of the alveolar ridge and facilitating optimal aesthetic and functional outcomes.
- 3. Periodontal Defects:** Alloplasts play a crucial role in the treatment of intrabony defects and furcation involvement, promoting periodontal regeneration.
- 4. Sinus Floor Augmentation:** In sinus lift procedures, alloplasts provide a stable scaffold for bone formation in the maxillary sinus, allowing for successful implant placement in the posterior maxilla.

Advantages of Alloplasts

- 1. Biocompatibility:** Alloplasts exhibit excellent biocompatibility, minimizing adverse reactions and facilitating integration with host tissues.
- 2. Controlled Composition:** The synthetic nature of alloplasts allows for precise control over composition, promoting consistent quality and reducing the risk of disease transmission.
- 3. No Donor Site Morbidity:** Alloplasts eliminate the need for a second surgical site, avoiding donor site morbidity associated with autografts.

Limitations and Considerations

- 1. Osteoconductivity:** While alloplasts provide a framework for new bone formation, their osteoconductive properties may be inferior to natural bone or other graft materials.
- 2. Resorption Rate:** Alloplasts may exhibit variable resorption rates, requiring careful consideration of the specific material and clinical context.
- 3. Cost:** The cost-effectiveness of alloplasts may vary depending on the specific material used.

Recent Advancements

Recent research has focused on enhancing the bioactivity of alloplasts by incorporating growth factors, peptides, or incorporating nanotechnology to improve their overall performance and integration with host tissues.

Conclusion

Alloplasts have become valuable additions to the periodontal armamentarium, offering clinicians a synthetic alternative with controlled properties and reduced morbidity. While they present certain advantages, careful consideration of their osteoconductive properties, resorption rates, and cost-effectiveness is crucial for optimal clinical outcomes. Ongoing research and technological advancements are expected to further refine the role of alloplasts in periodontal therapy.

Bone Grafting in periodontics has undergone a plethora of advancements and is routinely used in infrabony defects.

References

- Cypher, T. J., & Grossman, J. P. (1996). Biological principles of bone graft healing. *The Journal of foot and ankle surgery: official publication of the American College of Foot and Ankle Surgeons*, 35*(5), 413-7. doi:10.1016/s1067-2516(96)80061-5
- Bhatt, R. A., & Rozenal, T. D. (2012). Bone graft substitutes. *Hand clinics*, 28*(4), 457-68. doi:10.1016/j.hcl.2012.08.001
- Deshpande, S., et al. (2014). Vertical and horizontal ridge augmentation in anterior maxilla using autograft, xenograft and titanium mesh with simultaneous placement of endosseous implants. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*, 18*(5), 661-5. doi:10.4103/0972-124X.14246
- Moore, W. R., et al. (2001). Synthetic bone graft substitutes. *ANZ journal of surgery*, 71*(6), 354-61.
- Kübler, N. R. (1997). Osteoinduktion und -reparation [Osteoinduction and -reparation]. *Mund Kiefer Gesichtschir*, 1*(1), 2-25. doi: 10.1007/BF03043502. PMID: 9483923.
- Ellegaard, B., Karring, T., & Löe, H. (1974). New periodontal attachment procedure based on retardation of epithelial migration. *J Clin Periodontol*, 1*(2), 75-88. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051x.1974.tb01242.x. PMID: 4615110.
- Pandit, N., & Pandit, I. K. (2016). Autogenous bone grafts in periodontal practice: A literature review. *Journal of the International Clinical Dental Research Organization*, 8*(1), 27-33.
- Moskow, B. S., Karsh, F., & Stein, S. D. (1979). Histological assessment of autogenous bone graft: A case report and critical evaluation. *J Periodontol*, 50*, 291-300.
- Myeroff, C., & Archdeacon, M. (2011). Autogenous bone graft: Donor sites and techniques. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.*, 93*, 2227-36.
- Kao, S. T., & Scott, D. D. (2007). A review of bone substitutes. *Oral and maxillofacial surgery clinics of North America*, 19*(4), 513-21, vi. doi:10.1016/j.coms.2007.06.002
- Ellegaard, B. (1976). Bone grafts in periodontal attachment procedures. *J Clin Periodontol*, 3*(5), 1-54. PMID: 826549.
- Mellonig, J. T. (1992). Autogenous and allogeneic bone grafts in periodontal therapy. *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med.*, 3*, 333-52.
- Sullivan, H., Vito, A., & Melcher, A. (1971). A histological evaluation of the use of hemopoietic marrow in intrabony, periodontal defects. *Int Assoc Dent Res (Abstracts)*, 171.
- Dragoo, M. R., & Sullivan, H. C. (1973). A clinical and histologic evaluation of autogenous iliac bone grafts in humans. II. External root resorption. *J Periodontol*, 44*, 614-25.
- Brunsvold, M. A., & Mellonig, J. T. (1993). Bone grafts and periodontal regeneration. *Periodontol*, 1*, 80.
- Robinson, R. E. (1969). Osseous coagulum for bone induction. *J Periodontol*, 40*, 503-10.
- (1984). Particle size of periodontal bone grafting materials. *J Periodontol*, 55*, 406-9.

18. Froum, S. J., Thaler, R., Scopp, I. W., & Stahl, S. S. (1975). Osseous Autografts. I. Clinical responses to bone blend or hip marrow grafts. **J Periodontol*, 46*, 515–
19. Kolk, A., et al. (2012). Current trends and future perspectives of bone substitute materials—From space holders to innovative biomaterials. **J Cranio Maxillofac Surg.*, 40*, 706–718. doi: 10.1016/j.jcms.2012.01.002.
20. Bostrom, M. P. G., & Seigerman, D. A. (2005). The Clinical Use of Allografts, Demineralized Bone Matrices, Synthetic Bone Graft Substitutes and Osteoinductive Growth Factors: A Survey Study. **HSS J*, 1*, 9– doi: 10.1007/s11420-005-0111-5.
21. Nevins, M., et al. (2014). The efficacy of mineralized allograft cortical and cancellous chips in maxillary sinus augmentations. **Int J Periodontics Restor Dent*, 34*, 789–793. doi: 10.11607/prd.1720.
22. Toscano, N., et al. (2010). Horizontal Ridge Augmentation Utilizing a Composite Graft of Demineralized Freeze-Dried Allograft, Mineralized Cortical Cancellous Chips, and a Biologically Degradable Thermoplastic Carrier Combined With a Resorbable Membrane: A Retrospective Evaluation of 73 Consecutively Treated Cases From Private Practices. **J Oral Implant*, 36*, 467–474. doi: 10.1563/aaid-joi-d-09-00100.
23. Zhang, M., Powers, R. M., Jr., & Wolfenbarger, L., Jr. (1997). Effect (s) of the demineralization process on the osteoinductivity of demineralized bone matrix. **J Periodontol*, 68*, 1085–1092. doi: 10.1902/jop.1997.68.11.1085.
24. Özkan, Y., Akoğlu, B., & Kulak-Özkan, Y. (2011). Maxillary Sinus Floor Augmentation Using Bovine Bone Grafts With Simultaneous Implant Placement: A 5-Year Prospective Follow-Up Study. **Implant Dent*, 20*, 455–459. doi:10.1097/ID.0b013e3182386cbc.
25. Uzbek, U. H., et al. (2014). Bone Forming Potential of An-Organic Bovine Bone Graft: A Cone Beam CT study. **J Clin Diagn Res*, 8*, ZC73–ZC76. doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2014/8557.5352.
26. Kenney, E., et al. (1986). Bone formation within porous hydroxylapatite implants in human periodontal defects. **J Periodontol*, 57*, 76–83. doi: 10.1902/jop.1986.57.2.76.
27. Damien, E., & Revell, P. (2004). Coralline hydroxyapatite bone graft substitute: A review of experimental studies and biomedical applications. **J Appl Biomater Biomech*, 2*, 65–73.
28. Horch, H.-H., et al. (2006). Synthetic, pure-phase β -tricalcium phosphate ceramic granules (Cerasorb®) for bone regeneration in the reconstructive surgery of the jaws. **Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg*, 35*, 708–713. doi: 10.1016/j.ijom.2006.03.017.
29. Gallinetti, S., Canal, C., & Ginebra, M. P. (2014). Development and characterization of biphasic hydroxyapatite/ β -TCP cements. **Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 97*(4), 1065-1073.
30. Saikia, K. C., et al. (2008). Calcium phosphate ceramics as bone graft substitutes in filling bone tumor defects. **Indian journal of orthopaedics*, 42*(2), 169.
31. Lee, K. S., et al. (2009). Resorption Mechanism of Hydroxyapatite and β -Tricalcium Phosphate Coating Layer. **Key Engineering Materials*, 396*, 81-84.
32. de Grado, G. F., et al. (2018). Bone substitutes: a review of their characteristics, clinical use, and perspectives for large bone defects management. **J Tissue Eng*, 2018.*
33. Wang, W., & Yeung, K. W. (2017). Bone grafts and biomaterials substitutes for bone defect repair: A review. **Bioactive materials*, 2*(4), 224-247.
34. Skalleveold, H. E., et al. (2019). Bioactive glass applications in dentistry. **International journal of molecular sciences*, 20*(23), 5960.
35. Burguera, E. F., Xu, H. H., & Sun, L. (2008). Injectable calcium phosphate cement: Effects of powder- to- liquid ratio and needle size. **Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part B: Applied Biomaterials*, 84*(2), 493-502.
36. Kolk, A., et al. (2012). Current trends and future perspectives of bone substitute materials—from space holders to innovative biomaterials. **Journal of Cranio-Maxillofacial Surgery*, 40*(8), 706-718.
37. Xie, C., et al. (2012). The use of calcium phosphate-based biomaterials in implant dentistry. **Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine*, 23*, 853-862.
38. Haugen, H. J., et al. (2019). Bone grafts: which is the ideal biomaterial?. **Journal of clinical periodontology*, 46*, 92-102.
39. Yan, J., et al. (2011). Cross-linking characteristics and mechanical properties of an injectable biomaterial composed of polypropylene fumarate and polycaprolactone co-polymer. **Journal of Biomaterial Science, Polymer Edition*, 22*(4-6), 489-504. doi: 10.1163/092050610X487765. PMID: 20566042; PMCID: PMC3062160.